

World Safety Journal

A peer-reviewed journal,
published by the World Safety Organization

Journal Homepage:
<https://worldsafety.org/wso-world-safety-journal/>

COVID-19 Symptoms Differ Between Elderly and Young/Adult Patients, As Do Their Outcomes

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KEYWORDS

Pharmaceutical hazards
Antineoplastic drugs
Wipe samples
Industrial hygiene

ABSTRACT

This is a retrospective study of patients with new coronavirus pneumonia (COVID-19) who were admitted to Labib Medical Center, Sidon - Lebanon, and Jezzine Governmental Hospital, Jezzine - Lebanon, between January 15, 2020 and May 18, 2021. At both hospitals, there were 100 patients, 50 of whom were elderly (65 years or over) and 50 were young and middle-aged.

The study revealed that elderly patients were more likely to have a weakened immune system and comorbidities, as compared to patients under 65 years of age. During hospitalization, 50% of the elderly patients developed acute respiratory distress syndrome, compared to 24% for patients under 65 years of age; 100% of the elderly patients developed pneumonia, compared to 78% for patients under 65 years of age. Except for the troponin test, there were no significant differences between the two age groups in lymphopenia, leukopenia, thrombopenia, D-dimer, or CRP. Further, there was a substantial difference in the number of patients discharged with disability and the number of patients who died. The death rate in the studied population was 30%, with elderly patients accounting for 40%, and under 65 years patients accounting for 20%. During their stay at the hospital, elderly patients were more likely to have complications than under 65 years old patients.

1. INTRODUCTION

An outbreak of pneumonia with an unknown origin has been reported in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China, in December 2019. Following the outbreak, the World Health Organization (WHO) identified a novel coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2, as the pandemic causing virus in China and other areas of the world. With 170 million confirmed cases and 3.5 million resulting deaths in approximately 200 countries, Covid-19 is still spreading around the world. COVID-19 is thought to be

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related to severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS), which can be transmitted from animals to humans. However, contact with a local seafood dealer in Wuhan who illegally sold several wildlife creatures, including bats, has been linked to SARS-CoV-2 infection (Li J-Y et al., 2020)

COVID-19 infection causes a wide range of symptoms, including respiratory failure and organ failure, which can lead to death. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, a number of studies revealed that people of all ages are susceptible to SARS-CoV-2 infection; however, elderly people had greater positive rates in real-time reverse transcriptase-PCR (RT-PCR) assays and a larger hospitalization burden (Jiang F et al., 2020)

Patients with COVID-19 have been observed to have a higher rate of mortality and worse clinical outcomes than those with SARS. Because age is a host factor that increases the likelihood of severe COVID-19 infection and poor prognosis, it is crucial to better understand age-related susceptibility and pathogenesis. However, there is a scarcity of published evidence on age differences in COVID-19 clinical characteristics.

The low specificity of the symptoms most commonly associated with SARS-CoV-2 infection, on the one hand, and the presence of possible atypical or asymptomatic disease, on the other hand, are both issues in the clinical presentation of Covid-19. In fact, most of the signs and symptoms mentioned, such as fever, cough, or myalgia, can also be indicative of influenza or other prevalent respiratory illnesses, complicating the differential diagnosis of Covid-19 in both autumn and winter seasons.

1.1 Research Questions

The research questions addressed in this study are:

- Is there a difference in clinical characteristics between the under 65 years and the elderly COVID-19 patients?
- Why does the elderly population have a higher mortality rate than the young/adult population?

1.2 Hypotheses

In this study, we expected that aging and multimorbidity would impact the clinical presentation of SARS-CoV-2 infection. We also postulated that the patterns in which symptoms cluster together can form many symptom clusters, each of which could be more or less highly predictive of SARS-CoV-2 infection in persons under 65 years of age and the elderly.

1.3 Research Objectives

The study objectives are as follows:

- investigate the differences in COVID-19 clinical characteristics between the elderly and the under 65 years hospitalized patients, as well as their association with death rates.
- compare the clinical manifestations of COVID-19 in the two groups, in order to discover the age-specific clinical presentations of COVID-19.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The Corona Virus

2.1.1 Historical background

Since the 1918 flu pandemic, COVID-19 has become the fifth confirmed pandemic to be discovered. Its symptoms first appeared on December 1, 2019; fever, lethargy, dry cough, and dyspnea were among the symptoms associated with viral pneumonia (Huang C et al., 2020; Zhu N et al., 2020; Wu F et al., 2020). Due to location and pneumonia symptoms, the disease was initially dubbed Wuhan pneumonia by the media. The WHO ultimately declared COVID-19 a pandemic on March 11, 2020. The pandemic was later classified as SARS-CoV-2 by the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses (ICTV) based on phylogeny, taxonomy, and established practice (Coronaviridae Study Group, 2020).

A timeline of five pandemics since 1918 is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: A timeline of five pandemics

(Johnson N-P et al., 2002; Kain T et al., 2019; Simonsen L et al., 1998; Viboud C et al., 2016)

2.1.2 Definition

COVID-19 is a mild to severe respiratory illness caused by a coronavirus (Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome coronavirus 2 of the genus Beta coronavirus). It is spread primarily through contact with infectious material (such as respiratory droplets) or objects / surfaces contaminated by the causative virus, and is characterized by fever, cough, and shortness of breath.

Other symptoms of COVID-19 include fatigue, chills, body pains, headache, loss of taste or smell, sore throat, runny nose, nausea, vomiting or diarrhea, in addition to fever, cough and shortness of breath.

2.1.3 Clinical presentations

COVID-19 has a variety of effects on various persons. The majority of infected people will experience mild to moderate symptoms and recover without the need for hospitalization. It takes 5–6 days on average for symptoms to appear when a person is infected with the virus; it can also take up to 14 days.

2.1.3.1 Incubation period

The incubation period for COVID-19 is typically 14 days following exposure, with the majority of cases occurring four to five days later (Chan J-F et al., 2020).

2.1.3.2 Initial presentation

Cough, myalgia, and headache are the most commonly reported symptoms among patients with symptomatic COVID-19 infection. Other symptoms include diarrhea, sore throat, and changes in smell or taste. Fever, cough, dyspnea, and bilateral infiltrates on chest imaging are the most common symptoms of pneumonia (Huang C et al., 2020; Chen N et al., 2020; Wang D et al. 2020).

Although some clinical aspects (in particular, smell or taste abnormalities) are more common in COVID-19 than in other viral respiratory infections (Zayet S et al. 2020), there are no specific symptoms or indications that may reliably differentiate COVID-19 from other viral respiratory infections (Struyf T et al., 2020). However, the onset of dyspnea one week after the onset of the initial symptoms could be a sign of COVID-19.

A report of over 370,000 confirmed COVID-19 cases, with documented symptoms, to the CDC in the United States (Stokes EK et al., 2020) revealed the breadth of related symptoms:

- Cough, in 50 percent of the cases;
- Fever (subjective or $>100.4^{\circ}\text{F}/38^{\circ}\text{C}$), in 43 percent of the cases;
- Myalgia, in 36 percent of the cases;
- Headache, in 34 percent of the cases;
- Dyspnea, in 29 percent of the cases;
- Sore throat, in 20 percent of the cases;
- Diarrhea, in 19 percent of the cases;
- Nausea/vomiting, in 12 percent of the cases;
- Loss of smell or taste, abdominal pain, and rhinorrhea, in fewer than 10 percent each of the cases.

Patients with confirmed COVID-19 have reported a comparable spectrum of clinical symptoms in other cohort studies (Huang C et al., 2020; Wang D et al., 2020). Even in hospitalized groups, fever was not always evident on presentation. Fever was recorded in virtually all of the patients in one research study, but only around 20% of them had a low-grade fever of less than $100.4^{\circ}\text{F}/38^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Huang C et al., 2020). Fever (defined as an axillary temperature exceeding $99.5^{\circ}\text{F}/37.5^{\circ}\text{C}$) was present in only 44 percent of the 1099 Wuhan patients and other parts of China; however, it was detected in 89 percent of the time in patients during hospitalization (Guan WJ et al., 2020). Only 31% of COVID-19 patients hospitalized in New York had a temperature above $100.4^{\circ}\text{F}/38^{\circ}\text{C}$ at presentation, according to a study of over 5000 patients (Richardson S et al., 2020).

Smell and taste problems (such as anosmia and dysgeusia) have been reported more commonly in some

studies. The pooled prevalence estimates for smell and taste anomalies in a meta-analysis of observational studies were 52 and 44 percent (Tong JY et al., 2020).

In an Italian study of 202 outpatients with mild COVID-19 symptoms, 64 percent reported changes in smell or taste, with 24 percent reporting very severe changes; smell or taste changes were reported as the only symptom by 3 percent of the patients (Spinato G et al., 2020). The majority of subjective smell and taste abnormalities associated with COVID-19 did not appear to be permanent; for instance, in a four-week follow-up assessment of 202 COVID-19 patients in Italy, 89 percent of those who experienced smell or taste changes reported resolution or improvement (Boscolo-Rizzo P et al., 2020).

Gastrointestinal symptoms (e.g., nausea and diarrhea) were reported by certain patients (Huang C et al., 2020; Wang D et al. 2020), despite the fact that they were not reported in the majority of cases. In a systematic evaluation of studies, the pooled prevalence of gastrointestinal symptoms in individuals with confirmed COVID-19 was 18 percent, with diarrhea, nausea/vomiting, and abdominal pain reported in 13, 10, and 9%, respectively (Cheung KS et al., 2020).

Conjunctivitis was also reported (Colavita F et al., 2020). Falls, general health decline, and delirium had been reported in elderly patients, particularly those over 80 years of age and those with underlying neurocognitive deficits (Annweiler C et al., 2021).

2.1.3.3 Asymptomatic Infections

Infections that cause no symptoms have also been well documented (Oran DP, Topol EJ., 2020). According to one study, 33 percent of patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 never showed symptoms (Oran DP, Topol EJ., 2021). This estimate was based on four large population-based cross-sectional surveys, in which the median proportion of people who had no symptoms at the time of a positive test was 46 percent (**Range:** 43 to 77 percent). Depending on which specific symptoms were analyzed, the concept of "asymptomatic" differed between studies (Wang Y et al., 2020; Hu Z et al., 2020). Some people who were asymptomatic at the time of diagnosis acquired symptoms afterward (i.e., they were actually pre-symptomatic). Following the initial positive RT-PCR test, the symptoms appeared in a median of four days (**Range:** 3 to 7 days) (Sakurai A et al., 2020).

2.1.4 Symptomatic Infections

2.1.4.1 Acute course and complications

Infection symptoms can range from minor to life-threatening, as previously discussed. Over the course of a week, some patients with mild symptoms may show progress (Cohen PA et al., 2020). However, in 138 Wuhan patients hospitalized for pneumonia caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), five days following the onset of the symptoms (Wang D et al., 2020). In another research study, dyspnea appeared at a median of eight days (Huang C et al., 2020).

Generally speaking, COVID-19 has been linked to a number of problems, including:

A. Respiratory failure

Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) is the most common consequence in individuals with advanced illness, and can appear as soon as dyspnea begins. In the above-mentioned trial of 138 patients, 20% had ARDS within eight days of the onset of symptoms, and 12.3% required mechanical breathing (Wang D et al., 2020). Mechanical ventilation was required by 12 to 24 percent of the hospitalized patients in large trials conducted in the United States (Petrilli CM et al., 2020; Richardson S et al., 2020).

B. Cardiac and cardiovascular complications

Arrhythmias, myocardial damage, cardiac failure, and shock have been reported as complications (Wang D et al., 2020; Chen T et al., 2020; Rentz M et al., 2020).

C. Thromboembolic complications

Venous thromboembolism (VTE), which includes a widespread deep vein thrombosis (DVT) and pulmonary embolism (PE), is common in very unwell COVID-19 patients, especially in the intensive care unit (ICU), where rates between 10 and 40% (Ilaloglu S et al., 2020) have been reported. Acute stroke (even in individuals younger than 50 years old without risk factors) and limb ischemia have also been documented, as a result of arterial thrombotic events (Zhang Y et al., 2020).

D. Neurologic complications

COVID-19 encephalopathy is a common consequence, especially among critically sick patients; for instance, encephalopathy was identified in one-third of hospitalized patients. Strokes, movement problems, motor and sensory impairments, ataxia, and seizures occur in a smaller percentage of people (Liotta EM et al., 2020).

E. Inflammatory complications

With persistent fevers, elevated inflammatory markers (e.g., D-dimer, ferritin), and elevated proinflammatory cytokines, some patients with severe COVID-19 have laboratory evidence of an exuberant inflammatory response; these laboratory abnormalities have been linked to critical and fatal illnesses (Huang C et al. 2020; Mehta P et al., 2020).

There may be further inflammatory consequences including auto-antibody-mediated symptoms. For instance, the Guillain-Barré syndrome can develop 5 to 10 days after the onset of symptoms (Toscano G et al., 2020). In children with COVID-19, a multisystem inflammatory syndrome with clinical characteristics comparable to the Kawasaki illness and toxic shock syndrome has been identified. This illness is characterized by substantially increased inflammatory markers and multiorgan dysfunction (particularly cardiac dysfunction) (Morris SB et al., 2020).

F. Secondary infections

In general, secondary infections do not appear to be a common COVID-19 consequence. The reported rate of bacterial or fungal coinfections was 8% (in 62 of 806 cases) in a review of nine studies, mostly from China (Kubin CJ et al., 2021). These were primarily respiratory infections and bacteremia. Presumptive invasive aspergillosis has been reported in immunocompetent individuals with COVID-19 ARDS, while the prevalence of this complication is unknown (Koehler P et al., 2020). In a retrospective study from 16 health care centers in India between September and December 2020, there were 187 cases of Mucormycosis among approximately 12,000 patients hospitalized with COVID-19 (prevalence 0.27 percent overall, and 1.6 percent among ICU patients); the majority of the cases involved the rhino-orbital region (Patel A et al., 2021).

2.1.4.2 Recovery and long-term sequelae

The time it takes to recover from COVID-19 is very variable, depending on age, pre-existing comorbidities, and the severity of the sickness. Individuals with a slight infection should recover quickly (e.g., within two weeks); however, many people with severe disease will take longer to recover

(e.g., two to three months). Fatigue, dyspnea, chest pain, cough, and cognitive impairments are the most prevalent lasting symptoms. Findings also point to the possibility of long-term respiratory impairment (Van den Borst B et al., 2020) and cardiac complications (Rajpal S et al., 2021).

Some COVID-19 survivors have SARS-CoV-2 NAATs that are permanently or recurrently positive. Although recurrent infection or reinfection cannot be ruled out entirely in these circumstances, data suggests that it is improbable.

2.1.4.3 Laboratory findings

Lymphopenia, elevated aminotransaminase levels, elevated lactate dehydrogenase levels, elevated inflammatory markers (e.g., ferritin, C-reactive protein, and erythrocyte sedimentation rate), and abnormalities in coagulation tests are all common laboratory findings in COVID-19 hospitalized patients (Wang D et al., 2020). Even though the overall white blood cell count can vary, lymphopenia is a prevalent condition (Huang C et al., 2020; Chen N et al., 2020; Wang D et al., 2020). Many patients with pneumonia have normal serum procalcitonin levels when they are admitted; however, those who require ICU care are more likely to have increased levels (Huang C et al., 2020; Chen N et al., 2020; Wang D et al., 2020). Several laboratory findings have been linked to critical illness or fatality, including high D-dimer levels and more severe lymphopenia (Chen N et al., 2020).

2.1.4.4 Imaging findings

A. Chest radiographs

In early or mild illness, chest radiographs may be normal. In a retrospective study of 64 COVID-19 patients in Hong Kong, 20% did not have any abnormalities on chest radiographs at any stage during their illness (Wong HYF et al., 2020). Consolidation and ground-glass opacities were common abnormal radiograph findings, with distributions in the bilateral, peripheral, and lower lung zones; lung involvement increased over the course of the disease, with a peak in severity at 10 to 12 days following the symptom onset. The occurrence of spontaneous pneumothorax has also been reported; however, it is uncommon (Miró Ò et al., 2021).

B. Chest CT

Although chest computed tomography (CT) is more sensitive than chest radiography, and some chest CT results may be COVID-19-specific, no one finding can entirely rule in or rule out COVID-19. The American College of Radiology (ACR) in the United States advises against utilizing chest CT for COVID-19 screening or diagnosis (ACR Recommendations, 2020).

The most common finding on chest CT in COVID-19 patients is ground-glass opacification with or without consolidative abnormalities, which is consistent with viral pneumonia (Ojha V et al., 2020). The following anomalies were found in a systematic analysis of studies that analyzed the chest CT findings of over 2700 patients with COVID-19 (Bao C et al., 2020):

- Ground-glass opacifications – 83 percent;
- Ground-glass opacifications with mixed consolidation – 58 percent;
- Adjacent pleural thickening – 52 percent;
- Interlobular septal thickening – 48 percent;
- Air bronchograms – 46 percent.

A crazy-paving pattern (ground-glass opacifications with superimposed septal thickening), bronchiectasis, pleural effusion, pericardial effusion and lymphadenopathy, were among the less prevalent observations. COVID-19 chest CT abnormalities are usually bilateral, have a peripheral distribution, and affect the lower lobes. These results are typical in COVID-19, but they are not specific to it, and they are seen often in other viral types of pneumonias. Chest CT may be normal shortly after the onset of symptoms, similar to chest radiography, with abnormalities more likely to develop over the course of the disease (Pan F et al., 2020).

C. Lung ultrasound

When other imaging resources are not readily available, point-of-care lung ultrasonography has been described as a way to assess lung involvement in patients with probable COVID-19. Thickening, discontinuation, and interruption of the pleural line; discrete, multifocal, or confluent B lines visible under the pleura; patchy, strip, and nodular consolidations; and air bronchogram signs in the consolidations, have all been seen on lung ultrasound in patients with documented COVID-19 (Abrams ER et al., 2020).

2.1.5 Spectrum of severity and mortality rates

2.1.5.1 Spectrum of infection severity

The severity of symptomatic infection varies from moderate to critical, with the majority of infections being mild (Chan J-F et al., 2020; Bajema KL et al., 2020; Yang X et al., 2020).

According to a report by the Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention, which provided an estimate of disease severity based on 44,500 confirmed infections (Wu Z, McGoogan JM, 2020):

- 81 percent of people had a minor illness (no or mild pneumonia);
- 14% of people had severe illness (dyspnea, hypoxia, or over 50 percent lung involvement on imaging within 24 to 48 hours);
- 5% of people had a critical illness (such as respiratory failure, shock, or multiorgan dysfunction);
- The overall case mortality rate was 2.3 percent; no deaths in noncritical patients were documented.

Similarly, 14 percent of the 1.3 million cases reported by the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) through May 2020 required hospitalization, 2% were admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU), and 5% died (Stokes EK et al., 2020). The chance of developing a serious disease differed, depending on age and underlying comorbidities.

2.1.5.2 Mortality rates of COVID-19 infection

The case fatality rate solely reflects the mortality rate among instances that have been documented. Because many severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) infections are asymptomatic and many mild infections go undiagnosed, the infection mortality rate is much lower, with estimates ranging from 0.15 to 1% in some studies, with significant heterogeneity by location and risk group (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 28 July 2020; Ioannidis JPA, 2021).

The infection mortality rate was estimated to rise dramatically by age (0.002 percent at age 10, 0.01 percent at age 25, 0.4 percent at age 55, 1.4 percent at age 65, 4.6 percent at age 75, 15 percent at age 85, and over 25 percent at age 90), according to a systematic review and meta-analysis of 27 studies

from resource-rich settings that evaluated the total number of community infections through seroprevalence surveys or comprehensive tracing programs up to September 2020 (Levin AT et al., 2020).

The majority of the geographic variation in the reported infection fatality rates appear to be due to age-related variances. Death rates, for example, were greater in areas with a higher median population age).

2.1.5.3 Mortality rates among hospitalized patients

Hospitalized patients are at a significant risk of developing serious or deadly illnesses. In a study of 2,741 hospitalized COVID-19 patients, 665 individuals (24 percent) died or were discharged to hospice (Pettrilli CM et al., 2020). By the end of the study, 60 percent of 647 patients, who had invasive mechanical ventilation, died; 13 percent were still ventilated; and 16 percent had been discharged.

COVID-19 has been linked to a higher rate of in-hospital mortality than influenza. (Cates J et al., 2020; Verma AA et al., 2021). Patients with COVID-19 were found to be five times more likely to die during their stay than patients with influenza (21 percent versus 3.8 percent) (Cates J et al., 2020).

In a retrospective assessment of a national surveillance database in England, which included over 21,000 critical care patients with COVID-19, in-hospital mortality rates were reported to have been decreased over the course of the pandemic; ICU survival improved from 58 percent in late March 2020 to 80 percent in June 2020 (Dennis JM et al., 2021).

In resource-constrained situations, in-hospital mortality rates may be greater than previously reported. In one study from ten African countries, the in-hospital 30-day death rate, following critical care admission, was 48 percent (ACCCOS Investigators., 2021).

2.1.5.4 Excess deaths during the pandemic

Neither the case mortality rate nor the infection mortality rate is sufficient to account for the entire pandemic burden. Other factors, like delayed treatment, overwhelmed healthcare systems, and social determinants of health, contributed to the pandemic's excess mortality (Woolf SH et al., 2021; Islam N et al., 2021).

2.1.6 Risk factors for severe illness

Severe sickness can strike healthy people of any age, but it is more common in persons over the age of 65 years. Severe illness has also been linked to specific demographic characteristics and test abnormalities. In the sections that follow, these are examined in further depth. Based on epidemiologic, clinical, and laboratory data, several prediction techniques have been presented to identify patients who are more likely to experience severe illnesses.

2.1.6.1 Advanced age

SARS-CoV-2 infection can affect people of all ages, but it is most frequent in middle-aged and older adults; older adults are more likely to develop severe disease. In multiple cohorts of hospitalized patients with confirmed COVID-19, the median age ranged from 49 to 56 years (Huang C et al. 2020; Chen N et al., 2020; Wang D et al., 2020). According to a report by the Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention, which comprised around 44,500 confirmed infections, 87 percent of patients were between the ages of 30 and 79 years (Wu Z and McGoogan JM, 2020). Similarly, in a modeling study based on data from mainland China, the hospitalization rate for COVID-19 rose with age, with a 1% incidence for those between 20 and 29 years, a 4% rate for those between 50 and 59 years, and an

18% rate for those over 80 years (Verity R et al., 2020).

Older age is also linked to a higher risk of death (Wu Z and McGoogan JM, 2020; Richardson S et al., 2020; Williamson EJ et al. 2020). According to research by the Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention, case fatality rates for people aged 70 to 79 years and 80 years or over were 8 and 15%, respectively, compared to 2.3 percent for the overall cohort (Wu Z et al., 2020). According to a study from the United Kingdom, the risk of death among people aged 80 and over was 20 times higher than that of people aged 50 to 59 years (Williamson EJ et al. 2020).

In a study of 2,449 patients diagnosed with COVID-19 in the United States, between 12 February and 16 March 2020, it was shown that those aged 45 years and over accounted for 67 percent of the cases, with 80 percent of fatalities concerning those aged 65 years and over. In a comprehensive health care database analysis, persons aged 18 to 34 years accounted for just 5% of adults hospitalized with COVID-19, with a death rate of 2.7 percent; morbid obesity, hypertension, and male gender were all linked to mortality in that age range (Cunningham JW et al., 2020).

2.1.6.2 Comorbidities

The following comorbidities have been linked to severe illness and mortality (Wu Z, McGoogan JM, 2020; Petrilli CM et al., 2020; Williamson EJ et al., 2020; Cunningham JW et al., 2020):

- Cardiovascular disease;
- Diabetes mellitus;
- Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and other lung diseases;
- Cancer (particularly, hematologic malignancies, lung cancer, and metastatic disease) (Dai M. et al., 2020);
- Chronic kidney disease;
- Solid organ or hematopoietic stem cell transplantation;
- Obesity (Lighter J et al., 2020; Kompaniyets L et al., 2021);
- Smoking (Lowe KE et al., 2021).

In an Italian study of 355 COVID-19 patients who later died, the average number of pre-existing comorbidities was 2.7, with only three patients showing no underlying disease (Onder G et al., 2020).

2.1.6.3 Socioeconomic factors and gender

Certain demographic characteristics have also been linked to more serious sicknesses. In different cohorts around the world, males have accounted for a disproportionately high number of critical cases and deaths (Petrilli CM et al., 2020; Richardson S et al. 2020; Onder G et al., 2020).

In the United States and the United Kingdom, black, Hispanic, and South Asian people account for a disproportionately high number of COVID-19 infections and deaths, which is likely linked to underlying inequities in social determinants of health. Some studies (Kabarriti R et al., 2020; Muñoz-Price LS et al., 2020) that adjusted for comorbidities and socioeconomic status revealed no link between African-American or Hispanic ethnicity and poor COVID-19 results in hospitalized patients.

2.1.6.4 Laboratory abnormalities

Unfavorable outcomes have also been linked to specific laboratory characteristics.

These include (Wu C et al., 2020; Del Valle DM et al., 2020):

- Lymphopenia

- Thrombocytopenia
- Elevated liver enzymes
- Elevated lactate dehydrogenase (LDH)
- Elevated inflammatory markers (e.g., C-reactive protein [CRP], ferritin) and inflammatory cytokines (i.e., interleukin 6 [IL-6] and tumor necrosis factor [TNF]-alpha)
- Elevated D-dimer (>1 mcg/mL)
- Elevated prothrombin time (PT)
- Elevated troponin
- Elevated creatine phosphokinase (CPK)
- Acute kidney injury

In observational studies, deficiencies in several micronutrients, particularly vitamin D (Munshi R et al., 2021), have been linked to more severe illnesses.

2.1.6.5 Viral factors

Although other studies have identified no link between respiratory viral RNA levels and illness severity (Yilmaz A et al., 2021), patients with severe disease have been reported to have higher viral RNA levels in respiratory specimens than those with milder disease (Liu Y et al., 2020). The presence of viral RNA in the blood has been linked to serious illness, such as organ damage (e.g., lung, heart, kidney), coagulopathy, and mortality (Severe Covid-19 GWAS Group et al., 2020).

2.1.6.6 Genetic factors

Host genetic factors are also being studied to see whether they have any links to severe disease. One genome-wide association research, for example, discovered a link between polymorphisms in the ABO blood group genes and COVID-19 respiratory failure (type A associated with a higher risk) (Ray JG et al., 2020).

3. COVID-19 IN OLDER ADULTS

3.1 What is unique about COVID-19 and older adults?

COVID-19 is more likely to make older people quite unwell. When elderly people with COVID-19 become severely sick, they may require hospitalization, intensive care, or a ventilator to assist them to breathe, or they may even die. People in their 50s are at a higher risk, as are those in their 60s, 70s, and 80s. People aged 85 and over face the greatest danger.

COVID-19 poses a high danger to elderly patients due to physiologic changes associated with age, impaired immune function, and multimorbidity. Elderly people with respiratory viruses sometimes exhibit atypically, which can make diagnosis more difficult. In people over 70 years old, the median time from symptom onset to mortality is 11.5 days, compared to 14 days in younger people (Sohrabi C et al., 2020; Wang D et al., 2019).

According to a recent World Health Organization research, COVID-19 patients over the age of 80 years in China had a case fatality rate of 21.9 percent, while patients of all ages with no underlying chronic diseases had a fatality rate of only 1.4 percent (WHO-China Joint Mission, 2020). It should be remembered that concerns like insufficient ED or ICU care, as well as a lack of resources, can have a negative impact on mortality, and that age is just one of many such factors.

The very high danger of this virus in elderly patients is shown by new mortality statistics from Italy

(Wang D et al., 2019). In Italy, where 23% of the population is over 65 years, 89 percent of COVID-19 deaths concerned people over 70 years of age (31 percent were people between 70 and 79 years, and 58 percent were people over 80 years) (Stancati, 2020).

3.2 What is fever in older adults?

Should we screen for disease in elderly people using only a temperature of 100 degrees Fahrenheit? Fever is frequently used in COVID-19 symptom checks as a significant marker of disease. Fever is the most prevalent symptom, according to Chinese data, with 83 percent of 99 in-patients with a mean age of 55 (15 percent over 70) having fever (Chen N et al., 2020). Fever, on the other hand, may not be a sensitive enough indicator in elderly patients, as it is commonly dulled or absent even in the presence of a serious infection (High KP et al., 2009). In the absence of particular data from the growing COVID-19 outbreak, the sensitivity of fever in elderly patients is informed by influenza, a respiratory virus that causes high mortality in elderly patients. Only 32% of patients over 60 years old with documented influenza had triage temperatures above 100 degrees Fahrenheit, according to one ED research (Lam P-P et al., 2016).

For elderly patients, the Infectious Disease Society of America proposes changing the definition of fever to:

- a single oral temperature over 100° F, or
- 2 oral repeated temperatures over 99° F, or
- an increase in temperature of 2° F over the baseline temperature (Norman DC, 2000).

3.3 The aging immune system

One of the greatest predictors of whether a patient would develop mild or severe COVID-19 symptoms is the ability of managing viral load (Liu Y, 2020). The immune system must accomplish four major activities in order to successfully suppress and remove SARSCoV-2: (1) recognize, (2) alert, (3) destroy, and (4) clear. In elderly patients, each of these processes is known to be malfunctioning and more diverse (Fulop T, 2018; Franceschi C, 2017).

However, it is unclear which tasks are most important for COVID-19 advancement in elderly patients (Shen-Orr SS, 2013). The immune system undergoes two key alterations as we age. One is immunosenescence, a slow loss of immunological function that impairs pathogen identification, alert signaling, and clearance. This is not to be confused with cellular senescence, an aging-related condition in which old or defective cells stop reproducing and become epigenetically locked into a pro-inflammatory state, secreting cytokines and chemokines. The other common immune system that changes with age is inflammaging, a chronic increase in systemic inflammation caused by a hyperactive but inadequate warning system (Franceschi C, 2000). Immunosenescence and inflammaging are important drivers of the increased mortality rates in older patients, according to a plethora of fresh evidence documenting the pathology and molecular changes in COVID-19 patients. Both the innate and adaptive immune systems are affected by immunosenescence. Innate immunosenescence is marked by inadequate pathogen detection and activation of macrophages, as well as a decrease in natural killer (NK) cell cytotoxicity, whereas adaptive immunosenescence is marked by thymic atrophy and the formation of anergic memory cells. Pathogenic, genetic, and lifestyle factors that impact the epigenetic status of cells and the variety of immune cells are likely to be the cause of these age-related changes in both cases.

3.3.1 The aging innate immune system

The body's initial line of defense against coronaviruses is the innate immune system. Sentinel cells,

such as macrophages and dendritic cells, use single-pass membrane-spanning receptors termed Toll-like receptors (TLRs) produced on their cell surfaces to recognize structurally conserved viral proteins. In innate immune cells, defects in TLR activity have been shown to increase the severity of pneumonia in mice, particularly in the context of aging and chronic inflammation (Hinojosa E, 2009).

AMs (alveolar macrophages) are mononuclear phagocytes that patrol the lungs for dust, allergens, and pathogen remnants. AMs produce type I interferons when their TLRs detect an invader, which draw immune cells to the infection site and present antigens to lymphocytes (Li G, 2020; Shi Y, 2020). Although the number of AMs increases with age, their ability to switch between pro- and anti-inflammatory states is considerably diminished, as seen by a modest cytokine response upon TLR activation [fig2].

Figure 2: Ineffective clearance of SARS-CoV-2 infection

COVID-19 is likely accelerated in its early phases by the failure of AMs in older people to recognize viral particles and convert to a pro-inflammatory state, whereas in its mature stages, AMs are thought to be responsible for the excessive lung damage. In a recent study comparing the immune cell composition of bronchoalveolar lavage fluid from moderate and severe COVID-19 patients, researchers discovered that macrophages in severe cases were phenotypically more proinflammatory, expressing higher levels of C-C Motif chemokine receptor type 1 (CCR1) and C-X-C Motif Chemokine Receptor type 2 (CXCR2), which recruit other innate immune cells, compared to macrophages from moderate COVID-19 cases that expressed more T-cell attracting chemokines (Liao M et al., 2020).

Long-term monocyte activation has been linked to severe lung injury in rhesus monkeys, and increased numbers of pulmonary neutrophils and macrophages have been linked to the development of ARDS and greater lung damage in instances of SARS (induced by SARS-CoV-1).

Part of the reason for this could be a decrease in neutrophil activity, as these cells lose their ability to travel to infection sites and kill infected cells as they age. COVID-19 severity is unlikely to be caused by NK cells, a key component of innate immunity with potent cytotoxic action. Their numbers remain rather steady with age, and they were not required for proper viral clearance in a mouse model of

SARS (Glass WG, 2004). More extensive investigations of COVID19 patient autopsy tissue will be required to determine which of these cell types play the most damaging effects.

Mucins, protective glycoproteins found in mucosal barriers throughout the body, also alter in production and diversity with age, though their involvement in immunization against coronaviruses in humans is unknown.

3.3.2 *The aging adaptive immune system*

The adaptive immune system's immunosenescence is another factor that may influence whether a patient develops severe COVID-19. The thymus, which is located right above the heart and is the site of T cell formation and maturation of early thymic progenitors from the bone marrow, is one of the earliest tissues to age. The thymus shrinks by 40% by the age of 65 (Palmer DB, 2013), which coincides with the activation of the inflammasome component NLRP3 and Caspase-1, a pro-apoptotic protease (Majumdar S, 2018; Youm YH, 2012). The thymic microenvironment is deteriorated by the accumulation of intrathymic adipocytes, which further lowers thymic cellularity.

Thymic atrophy also leads to a decrease in naive T cells and an increase in memory lymphocytes, impairing immunosurveillance and exhausting B cells, cytotoxic T cells, and helper T cells (Ongrádi J, 2010).

Other common aging impacts on the adaptive immune system include a decrease in the creation of new naive T cells, a smaller TCR repertoire, T cell metabolic inefficiency, and lower T cell activation (Ron-Harel N, 2018; Salam N, 2013). CD8+ T cell clonal populations expand with age, restricting their variety, whereas CD4+ T cells retain a wide range of TCRs but suffer activation deficits (Salam N, 2013). Surprisingly, one study discovered that supercentenarians – people above the age of 110 years – contain an uncommon population of cytotoxic CD4+ T cells whose activation does not wane with age and can fulfill effector duties normally performed by CD8+ T cells (Hashimoto K, 2019). This T cell activity could explain why some elderly patients, even those over the age of 100, can survive COVID-19.

Not only does the quantity of T cells decrease with age, but so does their repertoire. Low T cell levels are becoming more common in those over 60, a condition known as lymphopenia (Diao B et al., 2020). Lymphoma in COVID19 patients is unlikely to be caused by direct SARS-CoV-2 infection (Zhou P et al., 2020), as it is in HIV patients because T cells express relatively low amounts of ACE2. One possible cause of T cell deficiency is immune system depletion caused by repeated viral exposures over a lifetime (Diao B et al., 2020; Zheng HY, 2020; Huang C et al., 2020). This theory is based on a number of studies that looked at the morbidity and mortality of adults over 60 who had been infected with the human cytomegalovirus for a long time (CMV).

CMV reemergence cycles were linked to extensive immune system remodeling, including significant exhaustion of CD8+ T cells, which was found to be a better predictor of all-cause death than chronological age.

T cell depletion is caused by a combination of infections and lifestyle factors, and not just CMV (Aiello A, 2019; Bartlett DB, 2012). Telomere shortening in viral-specific memory CD8+ T lymphocytes, which produces cellular senescence, a state of cell cycle arrest and hyper inflammation that precludes growth upon re-infection, is a primary cause of immunological fatigue at the chromosomal level. The fact that bronchoalveolar CD8+ T cells appear to have limited expansion potential (Liao M et al., 2020) and that peripheral blood T cells exhibit high amounts of the immune-exhaustion marker PD-1 in the most severe COVID-19 cases, lend credence to this notion (Diao B et al., 2020).

B lymphocytes, which make antibodies in response to coronavirus antigens (Li G, 2020), are similarly less diverse and sensitive as people get older. While the total number of B cells does not decrease with age, memory B cells increase and naive B cells decrease, perhaps leading to a loss of B cell repertoire diversity, though this has yet to be fully established in people. Changes in IgG glycosylation patterns, on the other hand, have been demonstrated to be closely linked to age and inflammation, and to predict the onset of age-related diseases. IgG N-glycans appear to be the most predictive of biological aging, although more research into B-cell internal and extrinsic glycosylation control in aging is needed.

3.3.3 *The Deficiency and Potential Roles of Vitamin D for the Immune System in elderly patients*

The immunological function is inextricably linked to one's dietary state. Vitamin D is one important nutrient that has attracted a lot of attention. The current SARS-CoV-2 pandemic has heightened concerns regarding vitamin D insufficiency as a risk factor and vitamin D supplementation as a nutritional assistance in the treatment of respiratory tract illnesses (RTIs).

About half of all elderly people have a vitamin D deficit, which lowers the efficacy of both adaptive and innate immune responses and raises the risk of infection due to a lack of sun exposure and decreased vitamin D production. Vitamin D levels in elderly are linked to immune characteristics such as the CD4+/CD8+ ratio and reduced levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines after stimulation (Meehan M, 2014; Sundaram ME, 2012). Although not all studies have found a benefit of vitamin D supplementation on the likelihood or duration of lower respiratory infections, a number of studies have shown its effectiveness, particularly in those who have an antibody shortage or are more susceptible to respiratory tract infections (Bergman P, 2015; Arihiro S et al., 2019).

Vitamin D treatment averted roughly 20% of acute respiratory infections, according to a recent meta-analysis of 25 randomized, placebo-controlled trials. As a result, some health professionals have suggested vitamin D supplementation for elderly people in general, as well as aged-care residents and critically-ill patients, as a method for increasing COVID19 survival rates.

The following examples illustrate crucial scientific information:

1. Both observational and interventional studies imply that vitamin D deficiency increases the incidence of RTIs and influenza in general (Beard JA, 2011). RTIs are more likely to occur in those who do not have enough vitamin D in their bloodstream.
2. Research suggests that supplementing with vitamin D can lessen the incidence of influenza (Grant WB et al., 2020) and other RTIs (Esposito S, 2015).
3. The vitamin D receptor (VDR) is found in respiratory epithelial cells, B and T lymphocytes, and other immune cells (such as monocytes, macrophages, and dendritic cells) (Sassi F, 2018). The VDR in these immune cells regulates antimicrobial molecule expression, which is important for infection management through modulating the innate and adaptive immune systems (Sassi F, 2018; Prietl B, 2013).
4. The involvement of vitamin D and VDR in lowering the inflammatory response by inhibiting the synthesis of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such IL-1, IL-1, and tumor necrosis factor- α (Ebadi M, 2020), which contribute to the severity of infection, are of special relevance (e.g. pneumonia). The presence of 1-hydroxylase (CYP27B1), an enzyme that converts 25(OH)D to 1.25(OH)D and is largely found in the kidney, in respiratory epithelium and immune cells, adds to the evidence that vitamin D plays a role in protecting against respiratory pathogen invasion.
5. Twenty-eight clinical trials to evaluate vitamin D and COVID-19 have been formally registered as of September 2, 2020 (WHO Trial Registry Network, 2020). Despite the fact that

randomized clinical trials have yet to validate the significance of vitamin D in lowering the risk and severity of COVID-19, numerous researches have demonstrated its effectiveness.

6. Vitamin D supplementation may minimize the risk of COVID-19 or severe COVID-19, according to (Grant WB, 2020; Baggerly CA, 2020).

While vaccines and other particular methods may be used to prevent and cure COVID-19, a well-functioning immune system is a requirement for overall health and aids in the protection of the human body against invading microorganisms. Given the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in diverse locations and populations, vitamin D consumption and circulation levels should not fall below the levels suggested by health care authorities and professional organizations. This may be especially critical among elderly people.

3.4 Preexisting medical conditions

The COVID-19 virus can infect people of all ages. The COVID-19 virus can infect both older and younger people. People over the age of 65 years, as well as those with pre-existing medical issues including asthma, diabetes, and heart disease, tend to be more susceptible to the virus. Cancer, chronic kidney disease, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), immunocompromised state, obesity, serious heart conditions, Type 2 diabetes mellitus, cerebrovascular disease, hypertension, and neurologic conditions, are all common among elderly people, according to CDC (US CDC, 2019).

If the severity of COVID-19 is determined by chest imaging for lung damage, D-dimer levels (Yao Y et al., 2020; Yu B et al., 2020), for coagulation status, virus loading and shedding duration for virus replication and clearance, and cytokine levels for cytokine storm, it is possible that most of these preexisting medical conditions are unrelated to the COVID-19 severity. Instead, as demonstrated in COVID-19 patients with COPD, cerebrovascular disease, cardiovascular disease, hypertension, and neurologic disorders, COVID-19 may aggravate these conditions. COVID-19 lung inflammation has the potential to degrade the remaining lung tissue and/or function in COPD patients; however, more research is needed to see if this can boost SARS-CoV-2 replication or speed up COVID-19 development.

Similarly, SARS-CoV2 can damage blood vessel endothelial and cause blood coagulation, which can exacerbate cerebrovascular and cardiovascular disorders. Cerebrovascular and cardiovascular illnesses, on the other hand, do not always promote virus multiplication or virus-induced tissue damage. Patients with diabetes who have hyperglycemia are more prone to bacterial infections, which can exacerbate the disease of COVID-19 patients. When glycemia is adequately controlled, however, the patients' susceptibility to bacterial infection is not increased, and COVID-19 may not be influenced by the diabetes status.

COVID-19 patients were shown to have a high prevalence of hypertension (Huang C et al., 2020; Richardson S et al., 2020), which could be due to increased ACE2 expression induced by the binding of SARS-CoV-2 spike protein to ACE2, or by other mechanisms (Bunyavanich S, 2020; Wang Z et al., 2018). The overexpression of ACE-2 may activate angiotensin, which raises blood pressure further. Fever, a frequent sign of viral infection, could potentially be linked to elevated blood pressure in COVID-19 patients. Intriguingly, it was discovered that giving ACE inhibitors to hypertensive patients could reduce the severity of COVID-19 (Kanwal A, 2020; Bean D et al., 2020).

3.5 Features of COVID-19 infection in elderly patients

Fortunately, the majority of COVID-19 cases are minor, with just a small percentage (about 14%) requiring hospitalization and oxygen support, and 5% requiring only admission to an intensive care unit

(China CDC, 2020). Multiorgan failure is the leading cause of death in severe COVID-19 patients, followed by acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), sepsis, and septic shock (Yang X et al., 2020).

Because elderly patients often have atypical clinical presentations, diagnosing and managing them will be difficult, with a high incidence of delayed diagnosis or misinterpretation, especially in cases of cognitive impairment, as well as a higher risk of infection spreading during COVID-19 outbreaks and a high mortality rate (Xue Za Zhi, 2020).

A number of studies have found that the most obvious symptoms at admission for COVID-19 infection in elderly were fever, cough, dyspnea and fatigue, which are common with any viral infection. Dyspnea was clearly the most commonly acquired symptom in patients who died (Verity R et al., 2019).

3.5.1 Atypical COVID 19 Presentations in Frail Older Adults

Despite the respiratory disease, typical COVID-19 symptoms such as fever, cough, and dyspnea may be missing in elderly patients (Jung YJ, 2017). Fever was present in only 20-30% of geriatric patients with infection (Jung YJ, 2017). Delirium, falls, widespread weakness, malaise, and functional deterioration are examples of atypical COVID-19 symptoms (Jung YJ, 2017). Conjunctivitis, anorexia, increased sputum production, dizziness, headache, rhinorrhea, chest discomfort, hemoptysis, diarrhea, nausea/vomiting, abdominal pain, nasal congestion, and anosmia are among the other symptoms (Dadamo H, 2020).

In elderly patients, tachypnea, delirium, unexplained tachycardia, or a decrease in blood pressure may be the presenting clinical symptoms (Dadamo H, 2020; Jarrett PG, 1995). Atypical presentation can be caused by a variety of factors, including physiologic changes with age, comorbidities, and the difficulty to provide an accurate history (Malone ML, 2020). Atypical presentation is more likely as people are older, frailer, and have more comorbidities (Jung YJ, 2017). Mild symptoms in elderly patients may be exaggerated in comparison to the severity of their illness (Jung YJ, 2017).

3.6 Outcome of COVID-19 infection in Elderly patients

Over 70% of the 339 COVID-19 infected patients, aged 60 years and over, were found to have a severe illness, a rapid rate of progression, and a high case fatality rate (19 percent). A symptom such as dyspnea, the presence of numerous comorbidities, such as cardiovascular disease and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), or complications, such as acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), were all linked to poor outcomes in elderly patients. Unfortunately, only a small percentage of elderly patients with ARDS, who were mechanically ventilated, did survive (Wu Z, 2020).

According to a retrospective examination of 82 COVID-19 deaths in Wuhan, China, more than half of the patients who died were over 60 years of age, accounting for 80.5 percent of all deaths, with a median age of 72.5 years. Males had a higher fatality rate (65.9 percent). Comorbidity was found in the majority of patients who died (76.8%), including hypertension in 56.1 percent, heart disease in 20.7 percent, diabetes in 18.3 percent, cerebrovascular illness in 12.2 percent, and cancer in 7.3 percent (Bicheng Z et al., 2020). As a result of the significant frequency of malnutrition in elderly patients and its impact on the immune system, nutritional evaluation and management should be given a top priority in determining the risk of infection, the course of the disease, and the outcome of the disease in elderly patients (Lipsitch M, 2020).

3.6.1 *Morbidity and mortality in elderly patients due to COVID-19*

COVID-19 epidemic has affected people of all ages. However, as compared to other age groups, it appears to have a higher influence on the health of elderly patients. According to an initial study from China and data from Italy, elderly patients had a higher probability of developing COVID-19 severe illness.

All COVID-19 cases reported through 11 February 2020 were evaluated by the China Center for Disease Control (CDC), which contained the records of 72,314 patients. According to the CDC findings, the severity of COVID-19 infection was shown to be higher in those aged 60 years and over. In populations aged 60 to 69 years, 70 to 79 years, and 80 years and over, the case fatality rate was 3.6 percent, 8 percent, and 14.8 percent, respectively. Similarly, an Italian study found that over 84 percent of the 7,587 people who died as a result of the disease were over 70 years of age.

During this time period, a good number of elderly patients were unable to receive competent care due to the fact that they were ranked lower on the priority list than their young counterparts, based on criteria that maximized the benefits in terms of the number of lives saved and the number of life-years saved. COVID-19 mortality was highest in elderly people aged 85 years and over (10 percent to 27 percent), followed by those aged 65–84 years (3 percent to 11 percent), and those aged 55–64 years (3 percent to 11 percent).

Those aged 20–54 years, on the other hand, had a mortality rate of less than 1%, with no deaths among teenagers. However, research has revealed that the severity of the disease is unevenly distributed among countries around the world. In many undeveloped countries, for instance, the severity and fatality rates were low. Despite having a large number of infected people, India had a lower fatality rate than in other parts of the world.

4. MATERIALS AND METHODS

4.1 Study population

A total of 100 patients with COVID-19 symptoms, who were admitted into hospitals between 15 January 2020 and 18 May 2021, were regarded in this study. The reason for the small size is that many hospitals refused to give us access to private information. Further, the country's economic and political status at the time of the study posed additional challenges, particularly with respect to transportation and the scarcity of gasoline. The ongoing power outage in Lebanon posed an additional problem, especially with respect to internet connection.

4.2 Statistical analysis

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 25) was used for data entry and analysis. All statistical tests were performed on a two-sided basis with a significance level of 5%.

5. RESULTS

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. The study population consisted of 100 patients who were split 50-50, see Figure 3, between two hospitals, namely: Labib Medical Center (LMC), Sidon -

Lebanon, and Governmental Hospital (JGH), Jezzine - Lebanon.

Figure 3: Distribution of patients at JGH and LMC

5.1 Demographic Characteristics

The patients were split into 65 males (65%) and 35 females (35%), see Figure 4.

Figure 4: Distribution of patients according to gender

The median age of patients was 61.6 years; the mean age was 61.6 ± 15.3 years. Patients were split 50/50, between elderly patients (65 years and over) and young/adult patients (under 65 years of age). Figure 5 shows the distribution of patients as a function of age.

Figure 5: Distribution of patients according to age

Young/adults (under 65 years of age) consisted of 30 males (60 percent) and 20 females (40 percent), with no statistically significant relationship between gender and age ($p = 0.295$), see Table 1. Elderly patients (65 years and over) consisted of 35 males (70 percent) and 15 females (30 percent). Body Mass Index (BMI) differed significantly by age group ($p = 0.002$), with 14 percent of elderly patients being underweight compared to 2% of young/adult patients; 24 percent of the young/adult patients were overweight compared to 2% of elderly patients.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics according to age

		Age		Total (N = 100)	p-value
		Less than 65 years (N = 50)	Equal and above than 65 years (N = 50)		
Gender	Male	30	35	65	0.295 ^a
		60.0%	70.0%	65.0%	
	Female	20	15	35	
		40.0%	30.0%	35.0%	

Table 1 (cont.): Demographic characteristics according to age

Body Mass Index	Underweight	1	7	8	0.002^a
		2.0%	14.0%	8.0%	
	Normal weight	11	7	18	
		22.0%	14.0%	18.0%	
	Overweight	12	1	13	
		24.0%	2.0%	13.0%	
	Obese	4	10	14	
		8.0%	20.0%	14.0%	
	Unknown	22	25	47	
		44.0%	50.0%	47.0%	

a) Chi-square test; Significance level set at 5%

5.2 Blood Type

Table 2 shows that there was no statistically significant relationship between age and blood type of the patients under study ($p = 0.337$). Out of the 100 patients under study, 25% had blood type A, 8% had blood type B, 11% had blood type AB, 10% had blood type O, and 46% were not tested.

Table 2: Blood type of patients according to age

		Age		Total (N = 100)	p-value
		Less than 65 years (N = 50)	Equal and above than 65 years (N = 50)		
Blood type	A	11	14	25	0.337 ^a
		22.0%	28.0%	25.0%	
	B	3	5	8	
		6.0%	10.0%	8.0%	
	AB	5	6	11	
		10.0%	12.0%	11.0%	
	O	8	2	10	
		16.0%	4.0%	10.0%	

Table 2 (cont.): Blood type of patients according to age

Unknown	23	23	46
	46.0%	46.0%	46.0%

a) Chi-square test; Significance level set at 5%

5.3 Symptoms

Prior to PCR, 94 percent of young/adult patients and 92 percent of elderly patients showed symptoms, with no statistically significant difference between the age groups ($p = 0.603$), see Table 3. The duration of the symptoms prior to PCR varied by age group ($p = 0.003$). Adult patients had a 16 percent incidence rate of symptoms 3 days ahead of PCR, while elderlies revealed a 28 percent occurrence rate. In young/adult patients, 78 percent of the symptoms appeared within 3 to 6 days of PCR, while in the elderly patients, 42 percent of the symptoms appeared within 3 to 6 days of PCR. Young/adults had a 4 percent occurrence rate of symptoms within 7 to 10 days following PCR, whereas the elderly patients exhibited an 18 percent incidence rate.

Table 3: Symptomatic onset prior to PCR according to age

		Age		Total	p-value
		Less than 65 years	Equal and above than 65 years	(N = 100)	
		(N = 50)	(N = 50)		
Symptomatic before PCR	No	3	3	6	0.603 ^a
		6.0%	6.0%	6.0%	
	Yes	47	46	93	
		94.0%	92.0%	93.0%	
	Unknown	0	1	1	
		0.0%	2.0%	1.0%	
Symptom duration before PCR	Less than 3	8	14	22	0.003 ^a
		16.0%	28.0%	22.0%	
	3-6 days	39	21	60	
		78.0%	42.0%	60.0%	
	7-10 days	2	9	11	
		4.0%	18.0%	11.0%	
	11-14 days	1	2	3	
		2.0%	4.0%	3.0%	

Table 3 (cont.): Symptomatic onset prior to PCR according to age

	More than 14 days	0	4	4	
		0.0%	8.0%	4.0%	
Symptoms onset before PCR in days	Mean (SD)	3.94 (2.22)	6.20 (7.86)	5.07 (5.86)	0.703 ^b
	Min - Max	0 - 12	0 - 41	0 - 41	
	Median [IQR]	4 [3-5]	3.5 [2-7]	4 [3-6]	

a) Chi-square test; b) Mann-Whitney U test; Significance level set at 5%

Table 4 reveals that young/adult patients had a hyperthermia rate of 56 percent whereas the elderly patients showed a rate of 20 percent, with sub-febrile temperature of 20 percent in young/adult patients and 34 percent in elderly patients; there was a statistically significant difference between the two groups ($p = 0.002$). With respect to chills, adult patients revealed a chill rate of 68 percent compared to 24 percent in elderly patients; the difference between the two groups was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Chest pain was reported by 24% of the study participants, with no statistically significant difference between the age groups ($p = 0.640$). Headaches were reported by 59 percent of the study participants with no statistically significant difference between the age groups ($p = 0.555$). Cardiac arrhythmia was found in 24% of the study participants, with no statistically significant difference between the age groups ($p = 0.160$).

Table 4: General symptoms according to age

		Age		Total (N = 100)	p-value
		Less than 65 years (N = 50)	Equal and above than 65 years (N = 50)		
Body temperature	No fever	12	21	33	0.002^a
		24.0%	42.0%	33.0%	
	Sub febrile temp	10	17	27	
		20.0%	34.0%	27.0%	
	Hyperthermia	28	10	38	
		56.0%	20.0%	38.0%	
	Alternation between hyper and hypothermia	0	2	2	
		0.0%	4.0%	2.0%	

Table 4 (cont.): General symptoms according to age

Chills	No	15	36	51	< 0.001 ^a
		30.0%	72.0%	51.0%	
	Yes	34	12	46	
		68.0%	24.0%	46.0%	
	Unknown	1	2	3	
		2.0%	4.0%	3.0%	
Chest pain	No	37	39	76	0.640 ^a
		74.0%	78.0%	76.0%	
	Yes	13	11	24	
		26.0%	22.0%	24.0%	
Headache	No	17	21	38	0.555 ^a
		34.0%	42.0%	38.0%	
	Yes	32	27	59	
		64.0%	54.0%	59.0%	
	Unknown	1	2	3	
		2.0%	4.0%	3.0%	
Cardiac arrhythmia	No	41	35	76	0.160 ^a
		82.0%	70.0%	76.0%	
	Yes	9	15	24	
		18.0%	30.0%	24.0%	

a) Chi-square test; Significance level set at 5%

Table 5 shows that cough rates varied by age group, with 90 percent concerning young/adult patients compared to 70 percent of elderly patients; the difference between the two groups was statistically significant ($p = 0.044$), Sputum was found in 13% of the study participants, with no statistically significant difference between the two groups ($p = 0.231$). Dyspnea was found in 89 percent of the study participants, with no statistically significant difference between the two groups ($p = 0.259$).

Table 5: Respiratory symptoms of patients according to age

		Age		Total (N = 100)	p-value
		Less than 65 years (N = 50)	Equal and above than 65 years (N = 50)		
Cough	No	4	12	16	0.044^a
		8.0%	24.0%	16.0%	
	Yes	45	35	80	
		90.0%	70.0%	80.0%	
	Unknown	1	3	4	
		2.0%	6.0%	4.0%	
Sputum	No	44	38	82	0.231 ^a
		88.0%	76.0%	82.0%	
	Yes	5	8	13	
		10.0%	16.0%	13.0%	
	Unknown	1	4	5	
		2.0%	8.0%	5.0%	
Dyspnea	No	7	3	10	0.259 ^a
		14.0%	6.0%	10.0%	
	Yes	43	46	89	
		86.0%	92.0%	89.0%	
	Unknown	0	1	1	
		0.0%	2.0%	1.0%	

a) Chi-square test; Significance level set at 5%

Table 6 reveals that elderly patients had lower oxygen saturation than young/adult patients, with a statistically significant difference between the two age groups ($p = 0.035$). Among young/adult patients, 28% had Spo2 above 94%, 46% had Spo2 between 90 and 94%, 18% had Spo2 between 80 and 89%, and 8% had Spo2 below 79%. Among the elderly patients, 12 percent had Spo2 above 94%, 46% had Spo2 between 90 and 94%, 12% had Spo2 between 80 and 89%, and 30% had Spo2 below 79%.

Table 6: Oxygen saturation of patients according to age

		Age		Total (N = 100)	p-value
		Less than 65 years (N = 50)	Equal and above than 65 years (N = 50)		
Oxygen saturation of patient	Spo2 below 70%	1	6	7	0.035^a
		2.0%	12.0%	7.0%	
	Spo2 between 70 and 79%	3	9	12	
		6.0%	18.0%	12.0%	
	Spo2 between 80 and 89%	9	6	15	
		18.0%	12.0%	15.0%	
	Spo2 between 90 and 94%	23	23	46	
		46.0%	46.0%	46.0%	
	Spo2 above 94%	14	6	20	
		28.0%	12.0%	20.0%	

a) Chi-square test; Significance level set at 5%

Table 7 shows that rhinorrhea was found in 10% of the study participants, with no statistically significant difference between the two age groups ($p = 0.182$). Conjunctivitis was found in 19% of the study participants, with no statistically significant difference between the two age groups ($p = 0.176$). Sore throats varied by age category, with 58 percent concerning young/adult patients and 10% concerning elderly patients, with a statistically significant difference between the two age groups ($p < 0.001$). Loss of taste or smell varied by age group, with 58 percent concerning young/adult patients and only 6% concerning elderly persons, with a statistically significant difference between the two age groups ($p < 0.001$).

Table 7: ORL symptoms of patients according to age

		Age		Total (N = 100)	p-value
		Less than 65 years (N = 50)	Equal and above than 65 years (N = 50)		
Rhinorrhea	No	44	43	87	0.182 ^a
		88.0%	86.0%	87.0%	
	Yes	6	4	10	
		12.0%	8.0%	10.0%	

Table 7 (cont.): ORL symptoms of patients according to age

	Unknown	0	3	3	
		0.0%	6.0%	3.0%	
Conjunctivitis	No	39	39	78	0.176 ^a
		78.0%	78.0%	78.0%	
	Yes	11	8	19	
		22.0%	16.0%	19.0%	
	Unknown	0	3	3	
		0.0%	6.0%	3.0%	
Sore throat	No	19	41	60	< 0.001 ^a
		38.0%	82.0%	60.0%	
	Yes	29	5	34	
		58.0%	10.0%	34.0%	
	Unknown	2	4	6	
		4.0%	8.0%	6.0%	
Loss of Taste or smell	No	20	43	63	< 0.001 ^a
		40.0%	86.0%	63.0%	
	Yes	27	3	30	
		54.0%	6.0%	30.0%	
	Unknown	3	4	7	
		6.0%	8.0%	7.0%	

a) *Chi-square test; Significance level set at 5%*

Table 8 reveals that diarrhea was more common in young/adult patients (44 percent) than in children (24 percent), with a statistically significant difference between the two age groups ($p = 0.035$). Young/adult patients (40%) were more likely than elderly patients (16%) to experience nausea and vomiting, with a statistically significant difference between the two age groups ($p = 0.035$). Abdominal pain was more prevalent in young/adult patients (40%) than in elderly patients (24%), with no statistically significant difference between the two age groups ($p = 0.086$).

Table 8: GI symptoms of patients according to age

		Age		Total (N = 100)	p-value
		Less than 65 years (N = 50)	Equal and above than 65 years (N = 50)		
Diarrhea	No	28	38	66	0.035^a
		56.0%	76.0%	66.0%	
	Yes	22	12	34	
		44.0%	24.0%	34.0%	
Nausea and vomiting	No	30	42	72	0.008^a
		60.0%	84.0%	72.0%	
	Yes	20	8	28	
		40.0%	16.0%	28.0%	
Abdominal pain	No	30	38	68	0.086 ^a
		60.0%	76.0%	68.0%	
	Yes	20	12	32	
		40.0%	24.0%	32.0%	

a) Chi-square test; Significance level set at 5%

Table 9 shows that a whopping 84 percent of the study participants reported fatigue and general weakness, with no statistically significant difference between the age groups ($p = 0.275$). Joint discomfort was reported by 30% of the study participants, with no statistically significant difference between the age groups ($p = 0.563$). Muscle pain was reported by 48 percent of the study participants, with no statistically significant difference between the age groups ($p = 0.230$).

Table 9: Musculoskeletal symptoms of patients according to age

		Age		Total (N = 100)	p-value
		Less than 65 years (N = 50)	Equal and above than 65 years (N = 50)		
Fatigue and general weakness	No	6	10	16	0.275 ^a
		12.0%	20.0%	16.0%	

Table 9 (cont.): Musculoskeletal symptoms of patients according to age

	Yes	44	40	84	
		88.0%	80.0%	84.0%	
Joint pain	No	35	34	69	0.563 ^a
		70.0%	68.0%	69.0%	
	Yes	14	16	30	
		28.0%	32.0%	30.0%	
	Unknown	1	0	1	
		2.0%	0.0%	1.0%	
Muscle pain	No	23	29	52	0.230 ^a
		46.0%	58.0%	52.0%	
	Yes	27	21	48	
		54.0%	42.0%	48.0%	

a) Chi-square test; b) Fisher Exact test; Significance level set at 5%

Table 10 reveals that the rate of falling-down symptoms was larger in elderly patients (28%) than in young/adult patients (6%), with a statistically significant difference between the two age groups ($p = 0.006$). The rate of delirium symptoms was higher in elderly patients (20%) than in young/adult patients (4%), with a statistically significant difference between the two age groups ($p = 0.028$). Elderly patients (48%) had a lower level of consciousness than young/adult patients (14%), with a statistically significant difference between the two groups ($p < 0.001$).

Table 10: Geriatric symptoms of patients according to age

		Age		Total (N = 100)	p-value
		Less than 65 years (N = 50)	Equal and above than 65 years (N = 50)		
Fall down	No	47	36	83	0.006^b
		94.0%	72.0%	83.0%	
	Yes	3	14	17	
		6.0%	28.0%	17.0%	
Delirium	No	48	40	88	0.028^b
		96.0%	80.0%	88.0%	

Table 10 (cont.): Geriatric symptoms of patients according to age

	Yes	2	10	12	
		4.0%	20.0%	12.0%	
Decrease level of consciousness	No	43	26	69	< 0.001^a
		86.0%	52.0%	69.0%	
	Yes	7	24	31	
		14.0%	48.0%	31.0%	

a) Chi-square test; b) Fisher Exact test; Significance level set at 5%

5.4 Medical History

In terms of medical conditions, elderly patients (86 percent) exhibited more problems than young/adults (62 percent), with a statistically significant difference between the two groups ($p = 0.006$). Cardiac issues were more common in elderly patients (54%) than in young/adult patients (20%), with a statistically significant difference between the two groups ($p < 0.001$). Congestive heart failure was found to be more common in elderly patients (30%) than in young/adult patients (10%), with a statistically significant difference between the two groups ($p = 0.012$). Coronary artery disease was found to be more common in elderly patients (40%) than in young/adult patients (18%), with a statistically significant difference between the two groups ($p = 0.015$).

Lung disease was found in 13% of the patients under participants, with no statistically significant difference between the groups ($p = 0.766$). Only 5 the elderly patients (10%) and 6 of the young/adult patients (12%) had chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Hypertension was found to be more common in elderly patients (74%) than in young/adult patients (28%), with a statistically significant difference between the two groups ($p < 0.001$). Diabetes were prevalent in elderly patients (54 percent) than in young/adult patients (28 percent), with a statistically significant difference between the two groups ($p = 0.008$).

A number of medical issues, such as obesity, cancer, renal illness, sleep apnea, etc., are listed in Table 11.

Table 11: Medical history of patients according to age

		Age		Total (N = 100)	p-value
		Less than 65 years (N = 50)	Equal and above than 65 years (N = 50)		
Health problem	No	19	7	26	0.006^a
		38.0%	14.0%	26.0%	
	Yes	31	43	74	
		62.0%	86.0%	74.0%	

Table 11 (cont.): Medical history of patients according to age

Cardiac problem	No	40	23	63	< 0.001^a
		80.0%	46.0%	63.0%	
	Yes	10	27	37	
		20.0%	54.0%	37.0%	
Congestive heart failure	No	45	35	80	0.012^a
		90.0%	70.0%	80.0%	
	Yes	5	15	20	
		10.0%	30.0%	20.0%	
Coronary artery disease	No	41	30	71	0.015^a
		82.0%	60.0%	71.0%	
	Yes	9	20	29	
		18.0%	40.0%	29.0%	
Lung disease	No	43	44	87	0.766 ^a
		86.0%	88.0%	87.0%	
	Yes	7	6	13	
		14.0%	12.0%	13.0%	
Sleep apnea	No	43	45	88	0.394 ^a
		86.0%	90.0%	88.0%	
	Yes	0	1	1	
		0.0%	2.0%	1.0%	
	Unknown	7	4	11	
		14.0%	8.0%	11.0%	
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	No	50	45	95	0.056 ^b
		100.0%	90.0%	95.0%	
	Yes	0	5	5	
		0.0%	10.0%	5.0%	

Table 11 (cont.): Medical history of patients according to age

Asthma	No	44	50	94	0.027^b
		88.0%	100.0%	94.0%	
	Yes	6	0	6	
		12.0%	0.0%	6.0%	
Hypertension	No	36	13	49	<0.001^a
		72.0%	26.0%	49.0%	
	Yes	14	37	51	
		28.0%	74.0%	51.0%	
Diabetes	No	36	23	59	0.008^a
		72.0%	46.0%	59.0%	
	Yes	14	27	41	
		28.0%	54.0%	41.0%	
Liver disease	No	48	49	97	1.000 ^b
		96.0%	98.0%	97.0%	
	Yes	2	1	3	
		4.0%	2.0%	3.0%	
Immunosuppressed	No	49	50	99	1.000 ^b
		98.0%	100.0%	99.0%	
	Yes	1	0	1	
		2.0%	0.0%	1.0%	
Obesity	No	25	31	56	0.124 ^a
		50.0%	62.0%	56.0%	
	Yes	7	10	17	
		14.0%	20.0%	17.0%	
	Unknown	18	9	27	
		36.0%	18.0%	27.0%	

Table 11 (cont.): Medical history of patients according to age

Cancer	No	46	47	93	0.695 ^b
		92.0%	94.0%	93.0%	
	Yes	4	3	7	
		8.0%	6.0%	7.0%	
Renal disease	No	46	43	89	0.338 ^b
		92.0%	86.0%	89.0%	
	Yes	4	7	11	
		8.0%	14.0%	11.0%	
Other comorbidities	Arrhythmias	0	2	2	
	Gastric ulcer	5	6	11	
	Carotid stenosis	0	1	1	
	BPH	1	4	5	
	Osteoporosis	0	1	1	
	Valvopathy and epilepsy	0	1	1	
	Rheumatism	0	1	1	
	Alzheimer	0	1	1	
	Thyroid disease	1	1	2	
	Epilepsy	1	0	1	
	Anemia	2	0	2	

a) Chi-square test; b) Fisher Exact test; Significance level set at 5%

5.5 Comorbidities

Seven (7%) of the 100 patients under study were on dialysis, with no statistically significant difference between young/adult patients (3%) and elderly patients (4%) ($p = 1.000$). With a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.040$), 19 (19%) of the 100 patients under study were treated with psychoactive medicine, which was split between 5 (10%) young/adults and 14 (28%) elderly patients. Further, with a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.001$), 66 (66%) of the 100 patients under study had poor eyesight, entailing 20 (40%) young/adult patients and 46 (92%) elderly patients. In addition, with a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.001$), 28 (28%) of the 100 patients under study had severe hearing loss, involving 4 (8%) young/adult patients and 24 (48%) elderly patients. Eight elderly patients (16%) required facility-based long-term care services, including assisted living, nursing homes. Further comorbidities (cerebrovascular accident or stroke, Parkinson disease, smoking, and drinking)

are presented in Table 12.

Table 12: Comorbidities of patients according to age

		Age		Total (N = 100)	p-value
		Less than 65 years (N = 50)	Equal and above than 65 years (N = 50)		
Dialysis	No	47	46	93	1.000 ^b
		94.0%	92.0%	93.0%	
	Yes	3	4	7	
		6.0%	8.0%	7.0%	
Living in nursing home or assisted living	No	50	42	92	0.006^b
		100.0%	84.0%	92.0%	
	Yes	0	8	8	
		0.0%	16.0%	8.0%	
Psychoactive medication	No	45	36	81	0.040^b
		90.0%	72.0%	81.0%	
	Yes	5	14	19	
		10.0%	28.0%	19.0%	
Impaired vision	No	30	4	34	<0.001^a
		60.0%	8.0%	34.0%	
	Yes	20	46	66	
		40.0%	92.0%	66.0%	
Impaired hearing	No	46	26	72	<0.001^b
		92.0%	52.0%	72.0%	
	Yes	4	24	28	
		8.0%	48.0%	28.0%	

Table 12: Comorbidities of patients according to age

Cerebrovascular accident or stroke	No	49	44	93	0.112 ^b
		98.0%	88.0%	93.0%	
	Yes	1	6	7	
		2.0%	12.0%	7.0%	
Parkinson disease	No	50	46	96	0.117 ^b
		100.0%	92.0%	96.0%	
	Yes	0	4	4	
		0.0%	8.0%	4.0%	
Current smoker	No	30	35	65	0.144 ^a
		60.0%	70.0%	65.0%	
	Yes	20	13	33	
		40.0%	26.0%	33.0%	
	Unknown	0	2	2	
		0.0%	4.0%	2.0%	
Alcoholic	No	43	44	87	0.044^a
		86.0%	88.0%	87.0%	
	Yes	6	1	7	
		12.0%	2.0%	7.0%	
	Unknown	1	5	6	
		2.0%	10.0%	6.0%	

a) Chi-square test; b) Fisher Exact test; Significance level set at 5%

5.6 Reason for Admission

Table 13 provides a summary of the reasons for admission. Dyspnea (31%), fever (9%), and fever plus dyspnea (16 percent) were the top three causes for admission.

Table 13: Reasons for admission according to age

	Age				Total (N = 100)	
	Less than 65 years (N = 50)		Equal and above than 65 years (N = 50)			
Dyspnea	13	26.0%	18	36.0%	31	31.0%
Fever	5	10.0%	4	8.0%	9	9.0%
Both fever and dyspnea	11	22.0%	5	10.0%	16	16.0%
Arrhythmia	1	2.0%	2	4.0%	3	3.0%
Arrhythmia and dyspnea	1	2.0%	1	2.0%	2	2.0%
Hyperglycemia	1	2.0%	0	0.0%	1	1.0%
Diarrhea	4	8.0%	0	0.0%	4	4.0%
Decrease level of consciousness	0	0.0%	6	12.0%	6	6.0%
Left side weakness	1	2.0%	2	4.0%	3	3.0%
General weakness	3	6.0%	0	0.0%	3	3.0%
Respiratory arrest	2	4.0%	2	4.0%	4	4.0%
GI bleeding	0	0.0%	1	2.0%	1	1.0%
Cardiac arrest	0	0.0%	1	2.0%	1	1.0%
Chest pain	2	4.0%	2	4.0%	4	4.0%
Hip fracture	0	0.0%	1	2.0%	1	1.0%
Both dyspnea and general weakness	4	8.0%	4	8.0%	8	8.0%
Cough	0	0.0%	1	2.0%	1	1.0%
Fall down	1	2.0%	0	0.0%	1	1.0%
DVT	1	2.0%	0	0.0%	1	1.0%

5.7 Hospitalization

The average number of days spent at the hospital was 9 ± 5.6 days for the elderly patients, compared to 7.8 ± 6 days for the young/adult patients, with no statistically significant difference between the age groups ($p = 0.067$). Acute respiratory distress was prevalent in 50% of the elderly patients, compared to 24% of the young/adult patients ($p = 0.007$). Pneumonia was prevalent in 100% of the elderly patients ($p < 0.001$), compared to 78% of the young/adult patients. Mechanical ventilation (MV) was applied by 34% of the elderly patients and 20% of the young/adult patients ($p = 0.115$), with an average duration

of 3.1 days by the elderly patients and 1.6 days by the young/adult patients ($p = 0.106$). Forty-two percent of the elderly patients and 22 percent of the young/adult patients ($p = 0.032$) required CPAP (see table 14).

Table 14: Hospitalization-related characteristics according to age

		Age		Total	p-value
		Less than 65 years	Equal and above than 65 years		
Days of hospitalization	Mean (SD)	7.82 (6.05)	9.00 (5.58)	8.41 (5.82)	0.067 ^b
	Min - Max	0 - 32	0 - 30	0 - 32	
	Median [IQR]	6 [4 - 8.5]	8.5 [5-11]	7 [5 - 10]	
Acute respiratory distress during hospitalization	No	38	25	63	0.007^a
		76.0%	50.0%	63.0%	
	Yes	12	25	37	
		24.0%	50.0%	37.0%	
Pneumonia	No	11	0	11	<0.001^c
		22.0%	0.0%	11.0%	
	Yes	39	50	89	
		78.0%	100.0%	89.0%	
Patient under mechanical ventilator	No	40	33	73	0.115 ^a
		80.0%	66.0%	73.0%	
	Yes	10	17	27	
		20.0%	34.0%	27.0%	
Days on mechanical ventilator	Mean (SD)	1.64 (5.01)	3.06 (6.17)	2.35 (5.63)	0.106 ^b
	Min - Max	0 - 32	0 - 30	0 - 32	
Extubation	No	9	17	26	0.127 ^a
		18.0%	34.0%	26.0%	
	Yes	1	0	1	
		2.0%	0.0%	1.0%	

Table 14 (cont.): Hospitalization-related characteristics according to age

		Unknown	40	33	73	
			80.0%	66.0%	73.0%	
Need of CPAP	No	39	29	68	0.032^a	
		78.0%	58.0%	68.0%		
	Yes	11	21	32		
			22.0%	42.0%	32.0%	

a) Chi-square test; b) Mann-Whitney U test; c) Fisher exact test; Significance level set at 5%

5.8 Laboratory Results

Seventy-five percent (75%) of the 100 patients under study had lymphopenia, which was evenly divided between 36 (72%) young/adults and 39 (78%) elderly patients, with no statistically significant difference between the two groups ($p = 0.488$). In addition, 48 (48%) of the 100 patients under study showed Leukopenia, with no statistically significant difference between the groups ($p = 0.230$), including 27 (54%) young/adults and 21 (42%) elderly patients. Thrombopenia was found in 27 (27%) of the 100 patients under study, with 17 (34%) young/adults and 10 (20%) elderly patients, with no statistically significant difference between the groups ($p = 0.115$). D-dimer levels were found to be abnormally high in 60% of the elderly patients and 40% of the young/adult patients ($p = 0.0132$). Troponin levels were high in 50% of the elderly patients and 24% of the young/adult patients ($p = 0.020$). CRP levels were high in 96% of the elderly patients and 94% of the young/adult patients ($p = 0.310$) (see Table 15).

Table 15: Laboratory findings in function the age group

		Age		Total	p-value
		Less than 65 years	Equal and above than 65 years	(N = 100)	
		(N = 50)	(N = 50)		
Lymphopenia	No	11	14	25	0.488 ^a
		22.0%	28.0%	25.0%	
	Yes	39	36	75	
		78.0%	72.0%	75.0%	
Leukopenia	No	23	29	52	0.230 ^a
		46.0%	58.0%	52.0%	
	Yes	27	21	48	
		54.0%	42.0%	48.0%	

Table 15 (cont.): Laboratory findings in function the age group

Thrombopenia	No	40	33	73	0.115 ^a		
		80.0%	66.0%	73.0%			
	Yes	10	17	27			
		20.0%	34.0%	27.0%			
D-dimer	Elevated	20	30	50	0.132 ^a		
		40.0%	60.0%	50.0%			
	Normal	14	10	24			
		28.0%	20.0%	24.0%			
	Not tested	16	10	26			
		32.0%	20.0%	26.0%			
	Troponin test	Elevated	12	25		37	0.020^a
			24.0%	50.0%		37.0%	
		Normal	13	11		24	
26.0%			22.0%	24.0%			
Not tested		25	14	39			
		50.0%	28.0%	39.0%			
CRP test		Elevated	47	48	95	0.310 ^a	
			94.0%	96.0%	95.0%		
		Normal	2	0	2		
	4.0%		0.0%	2.0%			
	Not tested	1	2	3			
		2.0%	4.0%	3.0%			

a) Chi-square test; Significance level set at 5%

5.9 Status at Discharge and Survival

Fifty-seven (or 57%) of the 100 patients under study were discharged without disability, including 36 (72%) young/adult patients and 21 (42%) elderly patients ($p = 0.002$). The death rate in the studied population was 30%, with 40% for the elderly patients and 20% for the young/adult patients ($p = 0.029$). On release, 6 percent of the 100 patients under study showed decreased cognitive function, 16 percent revealed decreased physical function, and 4 percent were transferred to a long-term facility.

Table 16: Status at Discharge and Survival according to age

		Age		Total (N = 100)	p-value
		Less than 65 years (N = 50)	Equal and above than 65 years (N = 50)		
Discharged without impairment	No	14	29	43	0.002^a
		28.0%	58.0%	43.0%	
	Yes	36	21	57	
		72.0%	42.0%	57.0%	
Death	No	40	30	70	0.029^a
		80.0%	60.0%	70.0%	
	Yes	10	20	30	
		20.0%	40.0%	30.0%	
Decrease cognitive function on discharge	No	49	45	94	0.092 ^b
		98.0%	90.0%	94.0%	
	Yes	1	5	6	
		2.0%	10.0%	6.0%	
Decrease physical function on discharge	No	46	38	84	0.054 ^b
		92.0%	76.0%	84.0%	
	Yes	4	12	16	
		8.0%	24.0%	16.0%	
Transferred to long term facility	No	49	47	96	0.617 ^b
		98.0%	94.0%	96.0%	
	Yes	1	3	4	
		2.0%	6.0%	4.0%	

a) Chi-square test; b) Fisher exact test; Significance level set at 5%

Cardiac arrest (16%), multi-organ failure (9%), respiratory arrest (19%), secondary infection (4%), and DIC were the leading causes of death (2 percent). The causes of mortality did not differ by age group ($p > 0.05$). (table 17).

Table 17: Death reasons according to age

		Age		Total (N = 100)	p-value
		Less than 65 years	Equal and above than 65 years		
		(N = 50)	(N = 50)		
Death from cardiac arrest	No	45	39	84	0.171 ^a
		90.0%	78.0%	84.0%	
	Yes	5	11	16	
		10.0%	22.0%	16.0%	
Death from multi- organ failure	No	46	45	91	1.000 ^b
		92.0%	90.0%	91.0%	
	Yes	4	5	9	
		8.0%	10.0%	9.0%	
Death from respiratory arrest	No	44	37	81	0.125 ^a
		88.0%	74.0%	81.0%	
	Yes	6	13	19	
		12.0%	26.0%	19.0%	
Death from secondary infection	No	49	47	96	0.617 ^b
		98.0%	94.0%	96.0%	
	Yes	1	3	4	
		2.0%	6.0%	4.0%	
Death from DIC	No	50	48	98	0.495 ^b
		100.0%	96.0%	98.0%	
	Yes	0	2	2	
		0.0%	4.0%	2.0%	

a) Chi-square test; b) Fisher exact test; Significance level set at 5%

6. DISCUSSION

Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) severity and outcome are largely determined by a patient's age. Elderly people over the age of 65 account for 80% of all hospitalizations and have a 23-fold higher risk of death than those under the age of 65. The world's aging population, particularly in light of the recent SARS CoV 2 pandemic, necessitates a deeper understanding of the challenges that may arise in the 65 and over age range.

In this study, 100 patients who were confirmed to have SARS-CoV-2 infection and were hospitalized at two hospitals: Labib Medical Center, Sidon - Lebanon, and Jezzine Governmental Hospital, Jezzine - Lebanon, were observed; fifty of the patients were over 65 years of age and 50 were under 65 years of age. Seventy percent of the elderly patients were male and 30% were female. With respect to the under 65 years age group, sixty percent were young/adult male patients and 40% were young/adult female patients.

According to this study, elderly patients exhibited a greater rate of chronic medical illness (86%) compared to 62 percent for young/adult patients; this result agrees well with that of previous research that determined that the frequency of comorbidities is higher in elderly patients than in young/adult patients (Xue Za Zhi, 2020). This study has revealed that the proportion of elderly patients with cardiovascular disease (54%), diabetes (54%) and hypertension (74%), was higher than that found in young/adult patients (28 percent, 28 percent and 20 percent, respectively). Congestive heart failure was found to be more common in elderly patients (30%) than in young/adult patients (10%); coronary artery disease was found to be more common in elderly patients (40%) than in young/adult patients (18 percent).

On admission, according to this study, the most prevalent symptoms in elderly patients were dyspnea, exhaustion, and general weakness, whereas the most common symptoms in young/adult patients were fever, cough, and fatigue. This shows that when infected with SARS-CoV-2, some elderly patients may not experience the same symptoms as young/adult patients, such as fever or cough. Due to a low basal temperature, disturbance in thermal homeostasis caused by aging, and the frequent use of drugs like aspirin, fever in elderly patients with bacterial or viral illness may be muted or perhaps absent. The difference between the aged groups lung structure, such as muscle atrophy, could well explain why elderly patients have worse airway clearance (Yao TT, 2020), lung reserve (Zuo MZ et al., 2020), and defensive barrier function (Xu J et al., 2020).

COVID-19 abnormal symptoms in elderly patients include falls, delirium, disorientation, dizziness, and unusual weariness. In this study, the rate of fall down symptoms was higher in elderly patients (28%) than in young/adult patients (6%); the rate of delirium symptoms was higher in elderly patients (20%) than in young/adult patients (4 percent). This suggests that atypical COVID-19 presentations should be considered during screening and testing of patients who are considered high risk due to age (Wang D et al., 2020).

Furthermore, when compared to young/adult patients, the incidence of severe or critically severe illnesses were higher in elderly patients. When persistent medical diseases, the probability of unusual symptoms, and the high incidence of severe sickness are factored in, senior patients require far more care and nursing during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Lymphopenia was a prevalent anomaly in elderly patients and young/adult SARS-CoV-2 patients, affecting 72 percent of elderly patients and 78 percent of young/adult patients. In this respect, studies have revealed that with beta coronavirus infections, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) and Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV), depressed lymphocytes were a common observation (Zumla A, 2016; Wong RS et al., 2003).

Other laboratory abnormalities, such as an elevated D-dimer, an elevated troponin level, and a high level of CRP, were more common in elderly COVID-19 patients than in young/adult patients. D-Dimer is a fibrinolysis specific marker that has been used to screen patients for venous thromboembolism, but it also promotes inflammation and may predict a bad sepsis prognosis (Mikuła T et al., 2018; Gris JC, 2011). In this study, 60 percent of elderly patients had an elevated D-dimer level, compared to 40% in young/adult patients. During hospitalization, however, no participants were diagnosed with venous

thromboembolism, suggesting that the high D-dimer was more likely connected with inflammation in the SARS-CoV-2 infection.

CRP has a critical function in innate immunity to pathogens (Slaats J, 2016). The number of elderly patients with high CRP levels was 96 percent, while the percentage of young/adult patients with elevated CRP levels was 94 percent, revealing the severity of the inflammatory process following SARS-CoV-2 infection. SARS-CoV-2 infection appears to have the potential to cause systemic damage to a patient's body. In this respect, it is critical to use laboratory testing to track organ function and the inflammatory response, especially in elderly COVID-19 patients.

When laboratory data were compared between young/adult and elderly patients, troponin levels were found to be increased by 50% in elderly patients, compared to just 24% in young/adult patients, indicating that the involvement of high sensitivity troponin in SARS-CoV-2 is critical; an increase in troponin could be linked to clinical disorders other than heart disease, such as pulmonary embolism, renal failure, or endothelial cell involvement in general (Varga Z, 2020).

According to this study, the mean hospitalization for elderly patients was 9 ± 5.6 days, compared to 7.8 ± 6 days for young/adult patients. Acute respiratory distress during hospitalization was seen in 50% of elderly patients, compared to 24% in young/adult patients. Pneumonia was found in 100% of elderly patients, compared to 78% in young/adult patients. COVID-19 patients over 65 years of age had a higher risk of respiratory failure and required more treatment time than COVID-19 patients under 65 years of age, indicating that elderly COVID-19 patients had considerably more severe disease and a poorer response to treatments than younger COVID-19 patients. This outcome coincides well with that of previous studies (Zhou F et al., 2020; Wang W, 2020).

When compared to young/adult patients, elderly patients received more invasive mechanical ventilation and CPAP/BIPAP. Mechanical ventilation (MV) was used by 34% of the elderly patients, with a mean duration of 3.1 days, and by 20% of the young/adult patients, with a mean duration of 1.6 days. Forty-two percent of elderly patients and 22 percent of young/adult patients required CPAP.

In terms of short-term outcomes, this study revealed that the overall death rate was 30%, with 40 percent for the elderly patients and 20 percent for the young/adult patients. The most common causes of death were respiratory arrest (19%), cardiac arrest (16%), multi-organ failure (9%), secondary infection (4%) and DIC (2%). The impact of age on mortality risk was found to be significant; patients between the ages of 75 and 84 years and those 85 years and above had 200 times and 630 times higher average death rates, respectively, than those between the ages of 18 to 29 years (CDC, 2020).

7. CONCLUSION

Lung infections are the most common symptom of the novel coronavirus. The stress on the heart is increased by lung infections. Multi-system illness characteristics that coexist in elderly people result in difficult and complex diseases. Other systemic complications, such as gastrointestinal bleeding, renal failure, disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) or deep vein thrombosis, delirium, and secondary infections, should be avoided because elderly patients are prone to multi-system organ dysfunction and even failure.

SARS-host CoV-2's receptor is found in a variety of human organs, including lungs, heart, neurological system, and skeletal muscles, which may explain why SARS-CoV-2 can cause harm to various organs. When compared to young and adult patients, elderly individuals are more likely to have substantial pulmonary and extrapulmonary organ damage, as well as a greater mortality rate. This could be owing to the fact that elderly people have more comorbidities and are malnourished. The mortality of elderly COVID-19 patients is linked to age, ARDS, acute cardiac damage, and heart failure. Given the higher

severity and lethality of COVID-19 in elderly patients, physicians should actively monitor and avoid any organ damage in order to improve their survival and reduce their mortality rate. According to this study, elderly Covid-19 patients who were hospitalized had more chronic comorbidities, less symptomatology (cough and fever), but more severe respiratory symptoms and cardiac enzyme abnormalities than the younger and adult patients.

Finally, with SARS-CoV-2 infection, elderly patients are more likely to have a severe or critically severe illness. When compared to the young/adult population, they may have uncommon symptoms and various organ problems, as well as a rapid and unexpected clinical deterioration. During hospitalization, elderly patients have greater complications than young/adult patients; with timely and appropriate care, they can have comparable favorable results to young/adult patients. In conclusion, careful nursing, observation, and systemic treatment are critical to elderly patients.

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